

Supplementary Material

Removal of phosphorus by modified bentonite:polyvinylidene fluoride membrane - Study of adsorption performance and mechanism

Xavier, Gabriela Tuono Martins ^{a,b}; Nunes, Renan Silva ^a; Urzedo, Alessandro Lamarca ^a; Tng, Keng Han ^b; Le-Clech, Pierre ^b; Labuto, Geórgia ^c; Mandelli, Dalmo ^a; Fadini, Pedro Sergio ^d; Carvalho, Wagner Alves ^{a,*}.

^a Center for Natural and Human Sciences, Federal University of ABC (UFABC), Santo André, Brazil.

^b UNESCO Centre for Membrane Science and Technology, School of Chemical Engineering, The University of New South Wales (UNSW), Sydney, Australia.

^c Department of Chemistry, Federal University of São Paulo (UNIFESP), Diadema, Brazil.

^d Department of Chemistry, Federal University of São Carlos (UFSCar), São Carlos, Brazil

*Corresponding author: wagner.carvalho@ufabc.edu.br; +55(19)99829-8929

Figure S.1 - Cross-sectional SEM image of 0.5 MB:PVDF and 0.75 MB:PVDF membranes, respectively.

Figure S.2 – Diagram of Fe(III) speciation in NaCl 0.7 mol L⁻¹ and H₃PO₄ dissociation.

